

**METHODS OF PROCESSING HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGES OF FOOD
AND LEGUMES****Mamatkulova Sadoqat**

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Abstract: Hyperspectral images summarize spatial and spectral details. They can provide valuable information on the internal chemical and physical properties of agricultural and food products in a rapid and non-destructive way. Despite rapid improvements in instrumentation and imaging techniques, high-quality hyperspectral images collected contain a lot of useless information such as uneven lighting, background, specular reflections, and bad pixels that need to be removed. That is, hyperspectral image preprocessing is necessary for almost every hyperspectral image to obtain pure images or pixels or to reduce negative effects on subsequent detection, classification, and prediction analysis. This manuscript lists some possible solutions to address the aforementioned issues before further image analysis. Advantages and disadvantages of different methods in solving a particular problem are also discussed. The resulting clean images or clean signals can be used for further data analysis. Finally, post-processing of hyperspectral images can be performed to improve the result of image classification or to

generate chemical images/distribution maps to show the spatial component concentration distribution of inhomogeneous samples.

Keywords: Hyperspectral image Pre-processing method Uneven illumination Post-processing method Distribution maps

Introduction.

Hyperspectral imaging (HSI), also known as “imaging spectroscopy” or “imaging spectrometry”, combines spectroscopic and imaging techniques in one imaging modality to get both spectral and spatial information simultaneously [1]. HSI has found vast applications in the quality and safety assessment of different agricultural and food products, such as fruit [2,3], vegetables [4,5], beef [6,7], lamb [8,9], pork [10,11], poultry carcass [12,13], fish [14,15], cereals [16,17], dairy products [18,19], and so on.

A hyperspectral image is composed by thousands or even millions of pixels. For example, the hyperspectral image with 200 wavelengths and 320 × 320 pixels for each waveband image contains 20,480,000 pixels. As a result, a large data storage space is needed to manage such a huge data cube. Moreover, one pixel’s spatial and spectral responses are similar to the neighboring pixels [20]. Data dimensionality reduction is often necessary to extract critical information and reduce storage space by removing redundancy. In addition, bad pixels or bad lines, and non-uniformity may also be introduced into hyperspectral images for the missing and/or abnormal behavior of a focal plane array [21]. The existence of these exceptional pixels may introduce unwanted noise and outliers to subsequent detection, classification, and prediction analysis [22]. Hence, carrying out effective pre-treatment methods is a necessary step to eliminate noises and avoid misinterpretation of the collected images. Moreover, since the characteristic feature of HSI is its high spatial spectral resolution ability, it is meaningful and necessary to study corresponding post-processing methods. These methods, such as display and enhancement, can highlight the spatial distribution of corresponding chemical composition and improve classification results of samples.

Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to provide a comprehensive overview of basic and commonly used pre and post-processing methods for hyperspectral image analysis of agricultural and food products. Specifically reviewing pre-processing methods about how to obtain clean images without non-homogeneous illumination, background, specular reflection regions, and abnormal pixels, and to obtain pure spectra from mixed spectral signals. Hyperspectral image post-processing aiming to generate, enhance, and finally display the detection result image will be overviewed in a relatively neat way.

Results and discussion.

Hyperspectral images contain three dimensions, including two spatial dimensions (X) and (Y), and one spectral dimension (λ). Thus, a hyperspectral image can be regarded as a stack of simultaneous images at each individual wavelength, or as a stack of spectra of all points in the image. Due to the differences of chemical components or inherent physical

characteristics, spectra of different objects tend to be displayed in different curves. For example in Fig. 2(c), spectra of background, specular reflection, and chicken breast meat are significantly different from each other. Based on this spectral signature, different materials can be identified and separated into different groups. Fig. 3 shows the acquisition methods of a hyperspectral data cube, which can be collected one spectrum of a single point at a time (whiskbroom), spectra of points of one line at a time (pushbroom), one waveband image at a time (tunable filter), even a full-wave band image at a time (snapshot), respectively. Among these four ways to acquire the volume of a three-dimensional data cube, snapshot is a non-scanning HSI which has no moving part and is able to record a full three-dimensional (two spatial, one spectral) hyperspectral data cube with each video frame. The pushbroom is the most commonly used acquisition mode for online applications in food industry by collecting spectra of line by line. A typical pushbroom line-scan HSI system consists the following parts: a charged coupled device (CCD) or complementary metal oxide

semiconductor (CMOS) camera, an imaging spectrograph with a C-mount objective lens, a translation stage, illumination sources, and a computer supported by image acquisition software [23]. The camera will collect the spatial and spectral information simultaneously, and spectrograph which is the heart of this detecting unit, will disperse the reflected light to different direction to generate spectral information. Common spectral ranges of HSI system locate in ultraviolet (UV, 200–400 nm), visible and near infrared (VNIR, 400–1000 nm), and near infrared (NIR, 900–2500 nm) region. The front lens will scan one spatial line (X) for each scan, and when the sample or the optical unit has moved line by line throughout the spectrograph, another spatial dimension (Y) is finished. Combined with spectral information (λ) of each point in each line, a complete three-dimensional hypercube can be generated fully. To acquire high-quality hyperspectral images, it is important to arrange each part of the system into proper location and set appropriate parameters. For example, the light source should give a uniform illumination over a large area to get rid of radiation damage, the imaging spectrograph and camera need to be carefully cooperated to get an accurate spectral dimension, and parameters of scanning speed, frame speed and exposure time need to be adjusted to cooperate with each other [24].

With the rapid development of software, it is not difficult to find proper software with powerful toolboxes to help researchers deal with their experiment results. As these software packages may have different characteristics and are good at diverse analysis aspects, when dealing with hyperspectral images, the selection of software is not unique. Environment for Visualizing Images (ENVI) (Exelis Visual Information Solutions, Boulder, CO, USA) is a powerful tool for the analysis of hyperspectral/multispectral images, which can provide many functions, such as data transformation, filter, classification, and visualization, and

Fig. 3. Acquisition methods of three-dimensional hyperspectral images

so on. MATLAB (The Math Works, Inc., Massachusetts, USA), which is also a powerful image processing tool, can develop image processing routines using high-level technical computing language and interactive environment. MATLAB can be used for analyzing data, developing models, and visualizing hyperspectral image data. The Unscrambler (CAMO Software AS, Oslo, Norway), another chemometric tool, gives users the power of multivariate data analysis and interactive data visualization in an easy-to-use program. There are also some other packages, such as MIA_Toolbox (Eigenvector Research, Wenatchee, WA, USA), which analyzes hyperspectral images using the familiar PLS_Toolbox tools (http://www.eigenvector.com/software/pls_toolbox.htm); and hyperSpec (R package) to handle hyperspectral images (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/hyperSpec/index.html>).

2. Hyperspectral image pre-processing

Affected by working conditions of devices, research environment, sample preparation, and other factors, acquired hyperspectral images usually contain some unsatisfied noises (e.g. uneven brightness, abnormal pixels, unwanted regions, and redundant data, etc.). All these noises may introduce incorrect and/or unrelated signals, and affect subsequent processing. Located on the top of hyperspectral image processing flow, data pre-processing has a direct and important impact on the quality of further analysis. The purpose of hyperspectral image pre-processing is to compensate non-homogenous illumination and to suppress influences of noisy pixels, irrelevant

regions, and redundant information as much as possible, so as to obtain pure images, non-mixed spectral signals, and to improve the subsequent data processing efficiency. Fortunately, as hyperspectral images contain both spectral and space information, some methods in fields of spectroscopy and image processing are equally applicable to hyperspectral data. This section introduces some frequently used pre-processing methods for solving problems encountered in hyperspectral images of food and agricultural products. And the pros and cons of each solution for specific problems are also discussed.

2.1.1. White and black calibration

For most cases, after hyperspectral images are collected under laboratory conditions, a pixel-level hyperspectral image calibration, also known as white and black calibration, will be carried out for two reasons. One is to convert the acquired light intensity into standard reflectance/transmittance value, the other is to remove random noise signals, which

are also known as “dark current”. Dark current caused by light source or power supply, can be generated due to the heat of internal CCD sensor, even when there is no light [25]. Pixel unit retains the harmful dark current and adds it to the produced signal. To correct the influence of dark current, two reference images, called white and dark images are captured individually from extreme illumination situations. A standard diffuse reflectance surface (e.g. sintered Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)) with a specific reflectance standard, and a completely turned off light source and blocked camera lens environment are used to take white and dark reference images, respectively [26].

It should be noted that, for the value of reflectance factor of white panel, the most commonly used option is 100%, but this is not the only choice. Wang et al. [27] applied a pixel-level calibration based on the reflectance values of a 75% Spectralon reflectance panel and a dark image to identify aflatoxin B₁ on maize kernel surfaces. And Khoshtaghaza et al. [28] used a white reference tile with 20% reflectance to

provide an estimate of incident light on the tile at each wavelength and to calibrate hyperspectral images of rainbow trout samples. The selection of a specific value of reflectance factor depends on the targeted samples that in which reference factor, a higher dynamic range of calibration images can be collected [29]. With the help of white reference and dark images, measured absolute reference values of each pixel can be changed to relative reference values by using the following equation:

$$R = \frac{I_m - I_d}{I_r - I_d} \times R_r$$

Where R is the calibrated relative reflectance value, I_m is the measured raw value, I_r is the measured value of the reflectance panel, I_d is the measured dark current, and R_r is the reflectance factor of the white panel.

Conclusion.

This paper has attempted to provide some basic and commonly used methods utilized in pre-processing, clean data analysis, and post-processing procedures of hyperspectral images analysis for agricultural and food products. Pre and post-processing methods were specifically emphasized. The aim of hyperspectral image pre-processing is to correct non-homogeneous illumination, to remove abnormal pixels and irrelevant regions, to compress data size, and to extract nonmixed spectra. The advantages and shortcomings of these recommended pretreatment methods when dealing with a specific kind of noise were also discussed. Image post-processing means to generate, enhance, and finally display the detection result image in order to visual observation of the spatial distribution of the composition or content of research object. Some examples were given to illustrate the effect of corresponding treatment methods, and some matters needing attention were also given next to the introduction of a specific method. In practice, the selection of specific pre-processing methods, multivariate chemometric processing steps, and proper post-processing methods should be based on the specific research object. For example, the type of agricultural products or food stuff to be processed, the different qualitative and quantitative

detection target of analyses, as well as the requirement and/or quality of detection result images.

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